

BEACONING Project

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Abstract

BEACONING stands for Breaking Educational Barriers with Contextualised, Pervasive and Gameful Learning and will focus on ‘anytime anywhere’ learning by exploiting pervasive, context-aware and gamified techniques and technologies, framed under the Problem-Based Learning approach.

BEACONING is a Horizon 2020 funded project of the European Union involving 15 partners - Grant Agreement 687676

In conjunction with 15 partners who each bring in their own expertise and technologies, the project seeks to pilot innovation in a real operational environment, aligning with DMLL’s ethos in disruptive media and the impact on changing mind-sets and creating new models and practices of teaching and learning.

The objectives of the project are:

1. Integrate technologies, pedagogical and social perspectives using pervasive, context-aware and gamified approaches ensuring that the BEACONING platform is innovative while also extending our scientific understanding and practice-based experiments of engaging a community of learners including those with disabilities with a more inclusive, connected and contextualised learning process.

2. Develop, implement and validate the BEACONING platform that: leverages cutting-edge approaches including the Future Internet technology, mobile, gamification, pervasive gaming, procedural game content generation, game authoring, human-computer interfaces, learning analytics and problem-based learning model; is usable, adaptable, extendable and sustainable.

3. Explore and measure the level of engagement, effectiveness and impact that is enabled by the BEACONING platform towards incentivising learners and fostering acquisition and transfer of knowledge and skills, validate this through large scale pilots involving a community of stakeholders and practitioners in Europe, and provide an exploitation and business plan for the platform adoption.

Web: <https://beaconing.eu>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/BeaconingEU>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/beaconing>

Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/c/BeaconingEuProject>

Keywords: Learning platform, gameful learning, Problem-Based Learning

1 Introduction

BEACONING is a teaching and digital learning platform that integrates technologies, pedagogical and social perspectives, using pervasive, context-aware and gamified approaches.

The lessons created by using the Authoring Tool demonstrate how easily the learning process turns into a pleasant, interesting and useful activity. The secret lies in using “context-aware” systems (that adjust to the context in which they are used) and gamification (translating a common learning context into a situation similar to a game). These methods make Problem-Based Learning possible.

Implemented within the Horizon 2020 program, the project seeks to pilot innovation in a real operational environment, while changing mind-sets and creating new models and practices of teaching and learning.

The project’s consortium is: Coventry University (UK), Heriot-Watt University (UK), BIBA - Bremer Institut Für Produktion Und Logistik GmbH (Germany), Inesc Tec (Portugal), Universidad Complutense De Madrid (Spain), Ort France (France), Succubus Interactive Sarl (France), Advanced Technology Systems (Romania), Imaginary (Italy), Geomotion Games Sl (Spain), Ifinity Spolka Z Organizzona Odpowiedzialnoscia (Poland), Playsoft (France), Sebit Egitim Ve Bilgi Teknolojileri Anonim Sirketi (Turkey), Hands Free Computing Limited (UK) and SIVECO Romania.

2 Project description

BEACONING sets a forefront in multifaceted education technologies through large-scale piloting of a digital learning platform that blends physical and digital spaces. As innovation action strategies, pilots combine opportunities for new ICTs in multiple ways that merge learning acquired in formal, non-formal and informal means, developing the skills for today’s abled and disabled learners and workforce.

The BEACONING platform will be a ubiquitous solution that exploits advances in user experience design, mobile communication, locationbased and context aware systems, procedural content generation, pedagogy-driven gamification, learning analytics and cloud technology through innovative integration towards a blended learning space.

The BEACONING demonstrator will facilitate, assess and author gamified learning activities, integrating existing educational tools and services of the participating organizations. Focusing on STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics), the cross-subject approach embedded in a Problem-Based Learning model will contextualize learning within real world problem solving and applications.

The role of learners is amplified in the process of filtering and connecting concepts framed under practical, investigative and exploratory scenarios. Large-scale pilots will validate and inform the development of the BEACONING ecosystem that democratizes learning across and among fully abled and those with mild to moderate physical and mental impairments (age 15 to 24), undergoing general and vocational training. BEACONING anticipates the benefits of making cross-subject matter more understandable, fostering the application of subject specialism to other domains. The pilot substantiates the technical and economic viability and the impact of the innovative platform to strategize market adoption and replication. By integrating experiences in a

highly engaging, contextualized and personalized manner, learning can go beyond the barriers of space and time.

Figure 1. Learning with BEACONING

3 The Authoring Tool

After Log in, the teacher will be met by the specific interface from where he can create, manage and assign his lessons:

Figure 2. The Teacher Interface

The Teacher App will provide teachers with an easy access to the Authoring Tool, where GLP can be built, edited and deployed.

In case that he want to edit/complete a lesson he will choose Edit option and he will enter in the Authoring Tool wich is the primary component that enables teachers as learning designers to author, edit and deploy lesson plans according to their specific needs.

Figure 3. The Lesson Manager

The dashboard of the Authoring Tool was developed to meet the specific needs of BEACONING including games and mini-games structure and location-based activities. It enables teachers to create Missions and Quests.

The Gamified Lesson Plans (GLP) constitute the core of the BEACONING Project and experience. The GPL embed learning in the daily life of the students, while providing deep engagement through their Game Plots overlaid over the pedagogical content.

BEACONING GLP (Gamified Lesson Plan) editing is very simple. Just pick a plot for the main game, observe the challenges that are essential opportunities for performance-based learning, then configure a selection of serious mini-games to exploit those opportunities for learning.

Figure 4. The Gamified Lesson Plans (GLP)

If the teacher choose a Lesson Path, for example, they will follow a linear path of quiz – like activities delivered through Mini Games like: - Drag it, Match it, Millionaire Quiz, Swipe and seek, Solve it, Checkers game, Location-based games, Planet Ninja and another few more.

The learning path can be gamified by associate it to the game plots and challenges.

Each plot has a number of events that can be assigned to specific exercises.

4 The Metagame

The Metagame lets users drag assets into a scene. The elements can be: a background image, a non-player character, a game item.

Figure 5. The Metagame

The Mini Games are reusable and configurable, provide engaging challenges to test and train player's STEM skills. They can be configured inside a lesson path, to be triggered at the end of another activity.

Figure 6. A Minigame example

Minigames will be integrated with the Learning Analytics and Core Services, enabling both adapting to student requirements and providing real time feedback. Minigames are a web based component that will be experienced by the student inside the Game App, more specifically, the minigames will be triggered by the interactions of the player with the game characters encountered during the gamified learning plan. A callback mechanism ensures that the Student App triggers the opening of the specific minigame session through a query string parameter.

The screenshot shows a web interface for editing a minigame. The title of the window is "Edit Activity". The form contains the following fields:

- Game Title ***: A text input field containing "Millionaire quiz". Below it is the label "Title of game visible to the player."
- Select the language ***: A dropdown menu with "English" selected. Below it is the label "language selection".
- Game Description**: A text input field containing "Millionaire quiz game. Try to answer correctly all the questions". Below it is the label "The description of this game visible to the player."
- Minimum score points to pass the game ***: An empty text input field. Below it is the label "Minimum score points to pass the game".

At the bottom of the form, there are three buttons: a green "Play" button, a white "Cancel" button, and a blue "Save" button.

Figure 7. Editing a minigame- Millionaire quiz

5 Students interface

The Student Dashboard is the main web page where students can get an overview of their progression within the different GLPs, and link with the Community. From this same web page students, will be able to access and launch LP (or specific activities and Quests) which have been activated and assigned to them by their teachers.

After log in, the students arrive in the homepage which provides information to help them decide where else in the application to go next: to the Library, to play the lessons or to connect to the community. They can create/edit their own profile. They can also consult the objectives set by teachers and see an overall progress of their activities.

Figure 8. BEACONING students interface

Beaconing also provides an experience not like any other with innovative tools for users with disabilities, such as a fully interactive toolbar interface called Accessabar, which makes content accessible to users with different disabilities.

Figure 9. BEACONING Accessabar

On the other hand the students can access their analytics. They can see a list of their missions and the STEM category of their missions and their status. Students can consult a list of their skills related to the given missions. They can see their current level, the badges collected so far and a list of the upcoming achievements.

Figure 10. BEACONING students analytics

6 References

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